

Supplementary material to the paper: Influence of Record-to-Record variability on the assessment of unreinforced masonry buildings.

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Abstract: A major source of uncertainty in the seismic assessment of existing masonry buildings lies in the definition of the seismic action. Such structures are typically evaluated through nonlinear quasi-static or dynamic analyses that primarily address epistemic uncertainties, while the record-to-record variability, which can significantly affect the statistical distribution of response estimates, is often neglected. This study investigates the influence of record-to-record variability on the seismic assessment of unreinforced masonry (URM) structures, considering a large population of pre-code masonry buildings representative of major urban centres in seismic-prone regions. The URM building stock is modelled in OpenSees using a three-dimensional macroelement formulation to capture the in-plane and out-of-plane response of masonry walls and simplified nonlinear material laws for interface elements. The seismic action is defined based on pre-defined seismological scenarios for multiple soil types. The combination of diverse building prototypes, defined in terms of plan configuration and number of storeys, and seismic intensity levels resulted in approximately 45,000 nonlinear dynamic analyses, performed through cloud computing. From these simulations, consistent capacity curves and empirical distributions of engineering demand parameters (EDPs) and intensity measures (IMs) were derived across different damage states (DSs). Empirical cumulative distributions expressing the probability of exceeding a given damage state for a specified IM are developed. A bootstrap-based framework is employed to quantify (*i*) the number of records required to ensure stabilisation of median and dispersion estimates under different convergence thresholds, and (*ii*) the minimum number of nonlinear analyses required to capture a target seismic demand with prescribed probability levels. The results provide practical guidance on the appropriate number of ground motions for nonlinear dynamic assessment of existing masonry buildings, balancing statistical robustness and computational efficiency.

KEYWORDS: Record-to-record variability; Pre-code masonry buildings; Out-of-plane (OOP) response; Convergence analysis; Cloud computing.

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FILES AND FOLDER ORGANIZATION

- 1. OpenSees model files (Tcl):** Input files required to reproduce the nonlinear response-history analyses performed in OpenSees for the five URM archetypes (a1, a3, b2, c1, c3) and for buildings ranging from 1 to 5 storeys.

Directory structure: /Prototypes/<Archetype>/<nP>/inputFiles/

where:

- <Archetype> = a1, a3, b2, c1, c3
- <nP> = 1p, 2p, 3p, 4p, 5p

Each inputFiles folder contains the following Tcl scripts:

- *Prototype_<Archetype>_<nP>_1_SelfWeight.tcl*
Performs the self-weight (gravity load) analysis.
- *Prototype_<Archetype>_<nP>_2_Modal.tcl*
Performs the modal analysis to extract eigenvalues and modal properties.
- *Prototype_<Archetype>_<nP>_3_Dynamic_template.tcl*
Template file used to generate the nonlinear dynamic analysis script for each ground-motion record and intensity level.
- *Prototype_<Archetype>_<nP>_batch.tcl*
Batch file that sequentially calls the self-weight, modal, and dynamic analyses.
- *Prototype_<Archetype>_<nP>_model.tcl*
Numerical model definition for the specified <Archetype>-<nP> combination, including geometry, macroelements, materials, boundary conditions, and analysis parameters.

- 2. Ground-motion input folders (grouped by soil type):** Acceleration time histories used as input motions, organised according to soil class.

Directory structure: /Records_<Soil>/<n>/

where:

- <Soil> = A, B, C, D, or ALL
(ALL includes records without Vs30 bounds)
- <n> = 1 to 30 (record identifier)

Each record folder contains:

- *n_E.txt*
Acceleration time history for the East–West (E–W) component.
- *n_N.txt*
Acceleration time history for the North–South (N–S) component.

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